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THE ROLE OF COMMUNICATIVE APPROACH IN STUDENTS LEARNING ENGLISH

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Annotation: *This article discusses the role of the communicative approach in teaching English, in particular English for special purposes, and suggests methods for using this approach. The use of a communicative approach in all language skills, including grammatical skills, leads to effectiveness in teaching English. The choice of authentic materials, taking into account the needs and interests of students, also contributes to their progress in learning.*

Keywords: *communicative language learning, communicative approach, communicative competence, grammatical competence, authentic materials, method, the dialogue, language skills*

РОЛЬ КОММУНИКАТИВНОГО ПОДХОДА В ИЗУЧЕНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА СТУДЕНТАМИ

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Аннотация: *В данной статье рассматривается роль коммуникативного подхода в обучении английскому языку, в частности английскому языку для специальных целей, и предлагаются методы использования этого подхода. Использование коммуникативного подхода во всех языковых навыках, включая грамматические навыки, приводит к эффективности преподавания английского языка. Выбор аутентичных материалов с учетом потребностей и интересов учащихся также способствует их прогрессу в обучении.*

Ключевые слова: *коммуникативное изучение языка, коммуникативный подход, коммуникативная компетентность, грамматическая компетентность, аутентичные материалы, метод, диалог, языковые навыки.*

The essence of the communicative method is to create real communication situations. When recreating the dialogue, the student has the opportunity to put into practice all the knowledge gained. The main goals of the communicative

method were the development of communicative competencies (i.e., learning to communicate in a language) and the development of all four language skills in combination (reading, writing, listening and speaking). This was very different from other approaches, for example, from grammatical translation, where listening and speaking were given a minimum of attention. A very important advantage of the communicative method is that it has a huge variety of exercises: role-playing games, dialogues, simulation of real communication are used here. At first, the communicative method was rejected, but now it again occupies a leading position along with the traditional grammatical and translation method. Most teachers prefer these two methods, and they are often used in combination. Working in a lesson based on a communicative methodology can include various types of tasks, but their main characteristic is that they solve a practical problem: for example, buy movie tickets, make an order at a restaurant or decide where to go on vacation. In particular, the Liltwood scientist identifies two types of tasks in the lesson: those aimed at functional communication and those aimed at social communication.¹ The first group includes tasks such as comparing pictures to find similarities or differences, arranging events according to pictures in the correct order, filling in gaps on a map or drawing, following instructions or solving a problem. The second group includes conversations, dialogues, role-playing games, improvisations or debates. The Communicative Approach develops all language skills – from speaking and writing to reading and listening. Grammar is mastered in the process of communicating in a language: the student first remembers words, expressions, language formulas and only then begins to understand what they are in a grammatical sense. The goal is to teach the student to speak a foreign language not only fluently, but also correctly. The rules and meanings of new words are explained by the teacher using vocabulary familiar to the student, grammatical structures and expressions, using gestures and facial expressions, drawings and other visual aids. Computers with CD, Internet, TV programs, newspapers, magazines, etc. can also be used. All this helps to arouse students' interest in the history, culture, and traditions of the country of the studied language. In the classroom, the teacher creates situations in which students communicate in pairs with each other, in groups. This makes the activity more diverse. Working in a group, students show speech independence. They can help each other, successfully correct the statements of the interlocutors. The teacher in the classroom assumes the functions of an organizer of communication, asks

¹Elukhina N.V. The role of discourse in intercultural communication and the methodology of formation of discursive competence. // IYASH. 2002, No. 3. pp. 9-13.

leading questions, pays attention to the original opinions of the participants, acts as an arbitrator in discussing controversial issues. The difference between communication is that instead of educational texts and dialogues specially adapted to the active vocabulary and grammar being studied, it uses imitation of real-life situations as the main technique, which are played out in the classroom in such a way as to cause maximum motivation for students to speak. So, instead of endlessly chewing over typical phrases from a textbook: "My name is Sopi. I live in Tashkent. I am a student", etc., students studying the topic of "Acquaintance" actually begin to actively get acquainted and discuss the issues they are interested in. The topics discussed are mainly those that students are familiar with in their native language: this makes it possible to focus specifically on the development of communicative abilities, that is, the ability to use the language spontaneously. Preferably, the topics should be "burning" – related either to the life of the students themselves, or to all aspects of modern life that are of interest to all (ecology, politics, music, education, etc.). In Western textbooks, especially at the level below Upper-Intermediate, you will hardly find such "topics" as Shakespeare's biography or achievements nuclear physics. Only at the senior levels are "bookish" and "scientific" styles introduced.

Unlike audio-lingual and other methods based on repetition and memorization, the communicative method sets exercises "with an open ending": students themselves do not know what their activities in the classroom will result in, everything will depend on reactions and answers.² New situations are used every day. This is how students' interest in classes is maintained: after all, everyone wants to communicate meaningfully on meaningful topics. Oral speech takes up most of the time in the lessons (although reading and writing are also given attention). At the same time, teachers talk less and listen more, only directing the activities of students. The teacher sets the exercise, and then, having "talked" the students, goes into the background and acts as an observer and arbitrator. Preferably, he should use exclusively the language he is learning. The communicative method consists in likening the learning process to the communication process, more precisely, it is based on the fact that the learning process is a model of the communication process, albeit somewhat simplified, but adequate in basic parameters, similar to the real communication process. All that has been said above regarding the communicative method of teaching speaking in

² Milrud R.P., Maksimova I.R. Modern conceptual principles of communicative foreign language teaching. // IYASH. 2000, No. 4. pp. 19-14.

a foreign language allows us to assert that the subject of study in this case is speech activity in English. In this method, the allocation of speech speaking skills is clearly traced, and exercises are offered for their consistent formation. The modern communicative method is a harmonious combination of many ways of teaching foreign languages, being probably at the top of the evolutionary pyramid of various educational methods. The use of a communicative teaching method removes the language barrier. Grammar is mastered in the process of communicating in a language: the student first remembers words, expressions, language formulas and only then begins to understand what they are in a grammatical sense.

The purpose of teaching a foreign language at the present stage is the acquisition of communicative competence, the components of which are:

- Language competence – involves mastering a certain amount of formal language knowledge and related skills related to various aspects of the language – vocabulary, phonetics, grammar.
- Speech competence - the ability to build communication in such a way as to achieve goals, in possession of various techniques for receiving and transmitting information both orally and in writing, compensatory skills. (the strategy of one's own communication and the selection of language tools for solving communication problems)
- Sociocultural competence – willingness and desire to interact with others, self-confidence, the ability to put oneself in the place of another and cope with the current situation – social; the ability to choose language forms, use them and transform them in accordance with the context - sociolinguistic.

Currently, learning oral communication, in which speaking plays a primary role, is one of the most important aspects of language. Oral speech in general and speaking as an integral part of it come to the fore. Students, first of all, want to learn how to speak the language. Learning outcomes are primarily assessed by the ability to communicate, in particular the ability to speak dialogically. The creation of a motivational base for teaching a foreign language is a necessary condition for the quality and success of learning and the formation of communicative competence.

Foreign language teachers are faced with the task of forming a personality that will be able to participate in intercultural communication. It is important to form a communicative competence that includes both linguistic and socio-cultural

competence. Knowledge of the socio-cultural background is very important, because without it it is impossible to form a communicative competence, even within limited limits. Therefore, it is necessary to have an idea of the socio-cultural characteristics of the country of the language being studied. The study of culture and language carries not only general educational ideas, but also at the same time ensures the development of personality, supports the motivation of students. Teachers are faced with the task of forming positive motivation, it is necessary to link it with the cognitive interests of students, the need to master new knowledge, skills, and abilities.

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